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MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACHING TECHNOLOGY WITH THE HELP OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the integration of digital technologies into the educational process, in particular, their use based on modern approaches in teaching technology. The effectiveness of forming practical skills in students through modern digital tools - interactive whiteboards, virtual laboratories, 3D modeling, artificial intelligence-based programs and online educational platforms is scientifically and theoretically substantiated.

Keywords: Digital technologies, technology, hybrid learning, virtual laboratories, artificial intelligence, gamification, project-based learning.

Introduction.

In the 21st century, digital technologies are fundamentally changing the field of education. The process of digitization, which is considered one of the priority areas of modern education, introduces new criteria into pedagogical approaches, teaching and methodological materials and methods of working with students. In particular, technology science — as a science focused on the formation of competencies in practical activity, design, project-based learning and problem-solving — is at the center of these changes.

The need to bring the content of technology science closer to modern production technologies, digital design, automation and engineering approaches requires the widespread use of innovative solutions and information and communication technologies (ICT) in teaching this science. In this context, the introduction of tools such as interactive platforms, multimedia resources, online classes, and learning systems based on artificial intelligence makes it possible to increase the efficiency of teaching technology science.

Methodology:

The methodological foundations used in teaching technology science using digital technologies are based on the transformed directions of modern pedagogy. In this scientific research, the constructivist approach was chosen as the main methodological basis. According to this approach, knowledge is formed by the student through independent research, experience acquisition and active participation. In particular, the practical and creative nature of technology science makes this approach relevant.

The study conducted a methodological analysis of digital tools in education - 3D modeling platforms (e.g. Tinkercad), virtual laboratories (Labster), online

engineering simulators (PhET), as well as interactive multimedia and gamification-based training sessions. It was observed how these tools affect students' ability to form technical thinking, develop design competence, and solve real-world problems using technological solutions. The study used a combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis methods. In the qualitative method, pedagogical observation, video recording of the lesson process, and interviews with teachers were used to study how modern technological tools are being implemented in practice. In the quantitative method, the results of pre-experimental and post-experimental tests were analyzed, and the differences between the groups of students trained using digital tools and those trained using traditional methods were statistically analyzed. Also, integrated learning environments created on the basis of modern didactic models - "Flipped Classroom", "STEM approach", "Project-based learning" were experimentally studied. It was found that these methodological approaches contribute to a high level of mastery, independent decision-making and the formation of digital competencies in students. In general, the methodological basis of the study is aimed at scientifically substantiating the inextricable link between the role of modern information and communication technologies in education, their didactic capabilities and practical results, which allows bringing the teaching of technology to an innovative level.

Literature review:

In recent years, scientific, technical and pedagogical research on the integration of digital technologies into the educational process has developed dramatically. The work of foreign scholars who developed the theoretical foundations of digital pedagogy — Marc Prensky, L. Johnson, and M. Fullan — shed light on the current issues related to the role of digital tools in modern education, the types of thinking characteristic of the digital generation, and the transformation of educational methodologies. The concept of "digital natives" put forward by Prensky emphasizes the need for modern, interactive, and adapted methods for students who are fully adapted to technological tools.

The studies of local scientists M. Jo'rayev, D. Nishonova and Kh. Rasulov analyzed the stages of introducing digital technologies into the education system of Uzbekistan, the impact of the use of ICT tools on the cognitive activity of students, as well as the adaptation of innovative approaches to the national education system. In particular, D. Nishonova's work entitled "Pedagogical Foundations of Digital Competencies and Information Culture" deeply covered the methodology for integrating digital technologies into teaching activities.

Many grant projects of the European Union and the USA (for example, the

"Modernization of Pedagogical Higher Education by Innovative Teaching Instruments - MoPED" project within the framework of the Erasmus+ program) have empirically proven how modern tools specific to technology (for example, Arduino, Tinkercad, 3D printers) can be used to form technical thinking in students.

The analyzed literature notes that approaches such as gamification, project-based learning, and problem-based learning are more effective when combined with digital tools. However, some sources emphasize that not only the technical mastery of digital tools, but also the correct application of pedagogical approaches is of crucial importance. Existing scientific sources provide important methodological and practical foundations for the formation of an innovative model of the educational process using digital technologies. However, within the framework of technological science, there is still a need for special integrated methodological approaches, models suitable for national conditions, and results based on experience. This article serves to fill this gap.

Discussion:

Teaching technological science using digital technologies has become an important part of the modern pedagogical paradigm. As the results of research have shown, approaches in this direction are significant in that they are not limited to the introduction of technical tools, but also require a fundamental renewal of the goals, content, forms and methods of the educational process. Therefore, digital tools used in technological science are not just technical resources, but also tools that serve to form students' independent thinking, ability to analyze problem situations, and creative solutions.

During the discussion, it was found that the effective use of digital tools depends on several key factors: first, the teacher must have high digital pedagogical competence; second, the educational process must be organized on the basis of integrated and interconnected approaches; third, the individual needs and level of preparation of students must be taken into account. For example, the use of gamification elements increases students' motivation, while project-based learning strengthens their practical skills. Also, approaches that serve to form students' reflective thinking in digital technology-based learning - blogging, creating a digital portfolio, participating in online discussion forums - are also of great importance. Students participating in such activities, in addition to mastering knowledge, also acquire the skills to analyze, evaluate and apply it in practice.

The results of the study show that the pedagogical effectiveness of the use of digital tools in technology plays an important role not only in conveying

knowledge, but also in preparing students for real-life situations, that is, in implementing the principle of “learning for life”. Therefore, the use of digital technologies in teaching technology should be considered as a comprehensive approach that serves the comprehensive development of the student’s personality.

Conclusion.

The results of the study show that digital technologies are an effective tool not only for modernizing the educational process in teaching technology, but also for forming students’ practical, creative and problem-solving competencies. The use of interactive platforms, 3D modeling programs, virtual laboratories and artificial intelligence-based learning systems makes the educational process visual, active and individualized.

Modern approaches - gamification, project-based learning, hybrid learning and flipped classroom methodology - bring the content of technology closer to practice, serve to develop students' independent thinking and professional readiness. In this, the digital pedagogical competence of the teacher is a decisive factor.

Based on this study, it was determined that in order to increase the effectiveness of digital tools in technology, they should be methodologically well-founded, adapted to the national education system and implemented in the activities of teachers through continuous professional development.

Therefore, digital approaches in teaching technology are a strategically important direction and should be recognized as one of the main factors in improving the quality of education, forming modern technical thinking in students and training personnel who meet the requirements of the digital economy.

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